

**MICROBIOLOGICAL MONITORING OF HOSPITAL STRAINS IN THE
OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT****Pardaev F.M.**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7813318>

Purpose of the study: study of the leading hospital strains and their circulation in the otorhinolaryngological department of Bukhara based on microbiological monitoring for 2019-2020.

Research material: The contents of surgical wounds were subjected to microbiological examination. The antibiotic sensitivity of microorganisms was determined by the disk diffusion method using the Mueller-Hinton medium.

Research results. Microbiological screening of wound contents made it possible to isolate in the structure of hospital strains in 2019.

the predominance of non-fermenting gram-negative bacteria (85%) and facultative anaerobic gram-negative bacteria *Proteus* spp (15%). In 2020, there is a change in the circulation of the main pathogens of nosocomial infection with a slight predominance of *Proteus* spp (53%) over non-fermenting gram-negative bacteria (47%). Comparison of the data obtained in the study of resistance showed a stable pattern of resistance of hospital strains to third-generation cephalosporins in 2019 (61%) and, respectively, in 2020 (62.6%), while an increase in antibiotic resistance to fluoroquinolones was noted in 2020 (30.2%) compared to 2019 (21%) resistant strains.

Conclusions: Hospital strains circulating in otorhinolaryngological departments retain a high level of resistance to antibacterial drugs, which complicates the problem of adequate antimicrobial therapy. At the same time, the role of microbiological monitoring increases for the formation of a strategy for the rational use of antimicrobial drugs and disinfectants.

References:

1. Karpova E.P., Martynova I.V. Treatment of rhinosinusitis in children with cystic fibrosis. *Russian otorhinolaryngology*. 2011; 3(52): 90–94.
2. Kobilov, E. E., & Raupov, F. S. (2016). Purposeful approach to the complex treatment of acute bacterial destructive pneumonia in children. In *Modern technologies in the diagnosis and treatment of surgical diseases of childhood* (pp. 47-52).
3. Lopatin A.S. Drug treatment of polypous rhinosinusitis. *Consilium medicum*. 2002; 9:461–468.

4. Lopatin A.S., Gamov V.P. Acute and chronic rhinosinusitis: etiology, pathogenesis, clinic, diagnosis and treatment principles. Moscow: Medical Information Agency, 2011: 8–59.
5. Martynova I.V., Karpova E.P., Kapranov N.I. Features of ENT lesions in children with cystic fibrosis. Questions of modern pediatrics. 2011; 10(5):49–53.
6. Ryazantsev S.V. Comparison of Russian standards for the treatment of acute sinusitis with the international program EPOS. Consilium medicum. 2008; 10:87–90.
7. Raupov, F. S., & Akhmedov, A. T. (2018). Modern complex treatment of acute destructive pneumonia in children. New day in medicine, (1), 21.
8. Raupov, F. S., & VOSIEV, J. J. // NEW DAY IN MEDICINE. Bukhara State Medical Institute, LLC "New Day in Medicine", (6), 236-239.
9. Raupov, F. S., & Mekhridinov, M. K. (2021). Results of complex treatment of acute bacterial lung destruction in children. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 146-149.
10. Larsen PL, Tos M. Origin of nasal polyps. The Laryngoscope. 1991; 101(3): 305–312.
11. Caimmi D, Matti E, Pelizzo G, Marseglia A, Caimmi S, Labo E, Licari A, Pagella F, Castellazzi AM, Pusateri A, Parigi GB, Marseglia GL. Nasal polyposis in children. J Biol. Regul. homeost. agents. 2012; 26(1) (Suppl.): S77–83.
12. Min YG, Jung HW, Kim HS, Park SK, Yoo KY. Prevalence and risk factors of chronic sinusitis in Korea: results of a nationwide survey. European archives of oto-rhinolaryngology: official journal of the European Federation of Oto-Rhino-Laryngological Societies (EUFOS): affiliated with the German Society for Oto-Rhino-Laryngology. Head and Neck Surgery. 1996; 253(7): 435–439.
13. Raupov, F.S. (2022, September). Preventive measures of complications of colon resection in children in consideration of morphological features. In "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" platform (pp. 41-42).
14. Fokkens W, Lund V, Mullol J, et al. European position paper on rhinosinusitis and nasal polyps 2012 (EP3OS). Rhinology. 2012; 50(23):1–299.
15. Zh, TS, & Raupov, FS (2022). Some morphological aspects of optimization of colon resection in children. International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research, 2(11), 42-46.
16. 16.A.T. Akhmedov, & Zh.R. Sharipov. (2023). THE ROLE OF CYTOKINES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research, 3(03), 59–67. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijmscr/Volume03Issue03-09>

17. A.T. Akhmedov, & L.A. Narziev. (2023). PREDICTORS OF CARDIOVASCULAR COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE AFTER BYPASS SURGERY. *International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research*, 3(03), 68–77. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijmscr/Volume03Issue03-10>
18. Ahmedov, A., & Kamolov, F. (2023). ECHOCARDOGRAPHIC CHANGES IN PATIENTS WITH A SURVEY OF PNEUMONIA ASSOCIATED WITH CORONAVIRUS INFECTION COVID-19. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(3), 110–115. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/883>
19. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). Physical activity and its impact on human health and longevity. *Достижения науки и образования*, (2 (82)), 120-126.
20. Джалилова, З. О., Хасанов, К. А., & Султонов, А. А. (2021). Роль научного управления в процессе обучения высококвалифицированных врачей в новом Узбекистане. *Молодой ученый*, (26), 377-379.
21. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF "HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 3(06), 53-64.
22. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaimonovich, D. S. (2023). Influence of the Mode of Work and Recreation of the Student's Health. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 2(3), 3-5.
23. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2023). Forming a Healthy Lifestyle for Students on the Example of the Volleyball Section in Universities. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(3), 22-25.

